

IMPLEMENTATION OF LOW COST VLSI ARCHITECTURE FOR HEVC USING BIT PLANE COMPRESSION TECHNIQUE

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Abstract

For the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) encoder, this brief proposes a new architecture based on very-large-scale integrated (VLSI) integer transforms. The signed bit-plane transform (SBT) matrices, which are produced from the bit-plane decompositions of the integer transform matrices in HEVC, constitute the basis of the architecture. From a mathematical perspective, multiple SBT matrices that just include binary 0 or ± 1 may be written as the binary weighted sum, yielding an integer transform matrix. Compared to the original integer transform, the bit width of the SBT matrices is smaller, and they are very simple. Similarly, the SBT matrices contain a large number of zeroes and are sparse. When it comes to preserving the SBT addition operators, the sparse property of SBT matrices is crucial. A lower-bit-width SBT matrix may be used to convert video data in the suggested architecture, as an alternative to the original integer transform in high-bit-width. With the suggested SBT, the transform unit circuit's latency may be greatly decreased.

Index Terms—VLSI architecture, integer transform, bit-plane matrix, ultra-high definition (HD), and High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC).

INTRODUCTION

With HEVC, the developers aimed to achieve compression efficiencies two times higher than those of H.264 / AVC, the prior standard. Many image and video compression algorithms, including JPEG, MPEG-2/4, and H.263, use the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). The fact that it can transform spatial domain data into frequency domain data is a big reason why it's so popular. After being modified, data will be compressed and any unnecessary information may be further deleted. When it comes to energy compression transforms, the DCT is thought of as the one that is most similar to the ideal K-L transform. There is a limited amount of bits used to represent real values in DCT matrix elements, which this raises the prospect of drift, defined as a discrepancy between the encoder's and decoder's decoded data. Newer video standards are starting to use integer transform to fix encoder/decoder mismatch and make low complexity implementations easier, such as H.264, VC-1, and AVS. The most recent innovation in HD video processing is High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) [3]. It is seen of as H.264's heir apparent. Compared to H.264, HEVC aims to be

50% more efficient while encoding. For this purpose, HEVC makes use of a plethora of cutting-edge coding techniques, such as the 4/8/16/32 integer transform. In both academia and business, developing effective methods for picture reduction remains a significant issue. It was later that ROM-based DA was used to build DCTs in order to minimise size, after multiplier-based DCTs had already been deployed. Then, because of the benefits of ROM-based, DA-based multipliers were used to generate partial products, and adders were set up to add these partial products. Words are moved and added in parallel in DA-based calculation for partial products. Directly truncating the least significant component introduces truncation error, which must be minimised. Statistical examination of the link between the partial product and the multiplier-multiplicand has led to the presentation of several error compensation bias strategies aimed at reducing the influence of truncation errors. In distributed computing, the multiplications are hidden by rearranging a multiply accumulate bit-by-bit. An effective method for shrinking the footprint of parallel hardware multiplication accumulates, it works well with FPGA designs. One common use of the discrete cosine transform (DCT) in digital image processing is picture transform coding, which involves compressing images. Digital signal representation has numerous benefits over analogue signal representation, but it requires a huge amount of bits for transmission and storage. As an example, in order to digitally encode and store a high-quality audio stream, about 1.5 megabits per second is needed. A lot more space will be needed for the forthcoming 1280 x 720 high-definition television (HDTV) with a frame rate of 60 fps. It will need almost 560 GB of storage space to digitise an hour-long colour movie with HDTV-quality footage. Nearly 45 MB of storage space is required for a digitised 14 x 17 square inch radiograph that was scanned at 70 pm. Raw digital signal transmission across low-bandwidth communication channels is very difficult, if not impossible.

ADVANTAGES OF DATA COMPRESSION

Compressing data has the primary benefit of lowering the storage needs. Additionally, it provides a promising method for making better use of the available bandwidth in data lines, which in turn lowers the transmission cost when delivering large amounts of data over long-haul links. As a result of the decrease in data rate, this helps to lower the cost of transmission considerably. In hierarchical storage systems, data compression in theory allows for quicker data storage at a higher level (sometimes with lower capacity), relieving pressure on the input-output channels.

DISADVANTAGES OF DATA COMPRESSION

Depending on the application area and the sensitivity of the data, data compression might have certain downsides in addition to its many benefits. This technique is highly sought-after in most data application fields. Decoding has a bigger influence on system performance than encoding does in big statistical or scientific databases when database updates are infrequent.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Overview of AVS-video coding standards.

Summary of key characteristics, adopted primary methodologies, and performance of the AVS video standard (created by the Audio Video Coding Standard Working Group of China) are provided in this publication. The growing need for HD and high-quality video services is the primary motivation for the present iteration of the AVS video standard. For digital storage and broadcast material, it offers a reasonable compromise between complexity and coding efficiency. In addition, it greatly improves coding efficiency and is readily applicable to current MPEG-2 systems due to its syntactic structure being identical to that of the MPEG-2 video standard.

A fast computational algorithm for the discrete cosine transform.

In comparison to traditional Discrete Cosine Transform methods that use the Fast Fourier Transform, a new Fast Discrete Cosine Transform technique reduces computing cost by a factor of six. This method was developed in may be easily converted to software or hardware implementations; they are presented in matrix form and shown by a signal-flow diagram.

EXISTING SYSTEM FUNCTIONAL MODULES

3.1 HEVC DESCRIPTION:

HEVC was developed with the goal of providing twice the compression efficiency of the previous standard, H.264 / AVC. Although compression efficiency results vary depending on the type of content and the encoder settings, at typical consumer video distribution bit rates HEVC is typically able to compress video twice as efficiently as AVC.

Figure 3.1 Different Types of Lossy Compression Techniques

Block Diagram of HEVC

Fig. 3.2. Block Diagram of HEVC

The proposed architecture for four-point integer DCT is shown in Fig. 3.3 It consists of an input adder unit (IAU), a shift-add unit (SAU), and an output adder unit (OAU).

Figure 3.3 Architecture for Four-Point Integer DCT.

The Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) has been widely applied in the area of image compression and video compression, such as JPEG, MPEG-2/4 and H.263. Its popularity is attributed to its ability to decorrelate data of spatial domain into data of frequency domain.

1-D Discrete Cosine Transform

Forward DCT

$$X(m) = u(m) \sqrt{\frac{2}{N}} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} x(i) \cos \frac{(2i+1)m\pi}{2N} \quad (1)$$

$$Z(u,v) = \frac{2}{N} C(u)C(v) \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} x(i,j) \cos \frac{(2i+1)u\pi}{2N} \cos \frac{(2j+1)v\pi}{2N} \quad (2)$$

written as:

Backward DCT

$$x(i) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{N}} \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} u(m) X(m) \cos \frac{(2i+1)m\pi}{2N}$$

2-D Discrete Cosine Transform

Where x (ij) is the image pixel data, and Z(u,v) is the transport data.

The forward and inverse 2-D DCT can be

$b_{1,i,j} b_{0,i,j} \} 2, b_{k,i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$. Then, there

$$d_{i,j} = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} (\text{sgn}(d_{i,j}) b_{k,i,j} 2^k), b_{k,i,j} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (1)$$

is the relation

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM

SIGNED BIT MATRIX-BASED TRANSFORM ALGORITHM:

A. Bit-Plane Decomposition of Integer Transform:

In order to narrow the bit width of intermediate transformed data, we propose the bit decomposition algorithm which decomposes the integer transform matrix into several SBT matrices.

Let $d_{i,j}$ be the element in the i th row and j th column in the $N \times N$ integer transform matrix DN , i.e., $DN = (d_{i,j})$. If $d_{i,j}$ is positive, the

binary expression of $d_{i,j}$ is $(b_{K-1,i,j}, \dots,$

where K is the number of binary significant bits of element $d_{i,j}$, $b_{k,i,j}$ denotes the k th bit of $d_{i,j}$, and $\text{sgn}(\ast)$ is the sign indication function that returns 1 for the positive value and -1 for the negative

value, i.e., $\text{sgn}(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x > 0 \\ -1, & x < 0 \end{cases}$. Thus (1)

can also be written as

$$-1, x < 0$$

$$d_{i,j} = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} (b_{k,i,j} 2^k), \quad b_{k,i,j} \in \{0, \text{sgn}(d_{i,j})\}. \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) is the signed integer binarization. If all elements $d_{i,j}$ in integer transform matrix D_N are binarized and all the k th bits of all binary $d_{i,j}$, $b_{k,i,j}$, $0 \leq i, j < N$, construct the k th bit plane, which is expressed in the form of $N \times N$ SBT matrix $B_{N,k} = (b_{k,i,j})$, there is Equation (2) is the signed integer binarization. If all elements $d_{i,j}$ in integer transform matrix D_N are binarized and all the k th bits of all binary $d_{i,j}$, $b_{k,i,j}$, $0 \leq i, j < N$, construct the k th bit plane, which is expressed in the form of $N \times N$ SBT matrix $B_{N,k} = (b_{k,i,j})$, there is

$$D_N = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} (B_{N,k} 2^k) \quad (3)$$

Where K is the binary bit width of the maximum element in matrix D_N , i.e., $K = \log_2 \max(d_{i,j})$. The matrix $B_{N,k}$ containing elements of 0 or ± 1 is just the SBT matrix. K SBT matrices are totally generated in the matrix decomposition.

possible element combination

situations of 2-SSBT is $2^2 = 4$. The

In the proposed adder reuse method,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \\ -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_j \\ x_{j+1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x_j + x_{j+1} \\ x_j - x_{j+1} \\ -x_j + x_{j+1} \\ -x_j - x_{j+1} \\ x_j \\ -x_j \\ x_{j+1} \\ -x_{j+1} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

the SBT $\rightarrow b_{k,i} \cdot \rightarrow x$ is split into L parts of sub-SBT $\rightarrow b_{l,k,i} \cdot \rightarrow x_l$ ($0 \leq l < L$), and their relationship is into multiple 2-SSBT vectors.

nine element combinations are (1, 1), (1, -1), (-1, 1), (-1, -1), (1, 0), (-1, 0), (0, 1), (0, -1), and (0, 0). As for the 2-SSBT vector, all possible addition operations for $\rightarrow b_{l,k,i} \cdot$

Fig. 4.1 . Hierarchical structure of SBT.

$\rightarrow x_l$ can be expressed as:

Fig. 4.2. Adder reuse circuit of 2-SSBT.

The number of all the

The inner circuit design of the 2-SSBT unit is described in Fig. 4.1. According to the relationship between M-SSBT and M/2-SSBT, the SBT can be implemented in a hierarchical way. An M-SSBT can be implemented through jointing two M/2-SSBTs. The hierarchical structure of 4-SSBT as an example is illustrated in Fig. 4.2 where the output of two 2-SSBT units is input to a 4-SSBT unit for 4-SSBT computation. The inner circuit design of the 4-SSBT circuit is also shown in Fig. 4.3. It can be summarized that the number of adders, #ADDER, used in the proposed adder reuse scheme for SBT can be calculated according to the expression

$$\#ADDER = \frac{\alpha^M - 1}{2} - \left(\alpha^{\frac{M}{2}} - 1 \right).$$

Fig. 4. Part of the adder reuse circuit of 4-SSBT

Taking 2-SSBT as an example, M = 2, and $\alpha = 3$; thus, the number of adders of a 2-SSBT is 2.

Fig. 5. One-dimensional 32×32 transform top-level architecture.

VI. RESULTS

The Verilog HDL Modules have successfully simulate, verified and synthesized using Xilinxise14.5.

EXISTING RESULTS:

RTL SCHEMATIC:

TECHNOLOGY SCHEMATIC:

DESIGN SUMMARY:

Device Utilization Summary (estimated values)			
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Slices	140	466	30%
Number of 4 input LUTs	266	932	28%
Number of bonded IOBs	674	232	290%
Number of GCLs	1	24	4%

TIMING SUMMARY:

```

Timing constraint: Default OFFSET OUT AFTER for Clock 'CLK'
Total number of paths / destination ports: 384 / 384
-----
Offset:          4.040ns (Levels of Logic = 1)
Source:          m2/Mby2SSBT2/YOUT_11 (FF)
Destination:    Z10<11> (PAD)
Source Clock:   CLK rising

Data Path: m2/Mby2SSBT2/YOUT_11 to Z10<11>
Cell:in->out    fanout  Gate  Net  Logical Name (Net Name)
-----
FDR:C->Q        1      0.514 0.357 m2/Mby2SSBT2/YOUT_11 (m2/Mby2SSBT2/YOUT_11)
OBUF:I->O       3.169          Z10_11_OBUF (Z10<11>)
-----
Total              4.040ns (3.683ns logic, 0.357ns route)
                    (91.2% logic, 8.8% route)
    
```

PROPOSED RESULTS:

SYNTHESIS RESULT:

Name	Value	999,994 ps	999,995 ps	999,996 ps	999,997 ps	999,998 ps	999,999 ps
Z0[1:0]	010001001110				010001001110		
Z1[1:0]	001111000011				001111000011		
Z2[1:0]	111011011110				111011011110		
Z3[1:0]	101000001110				101000001110		
Z4[1:0]	100100011111				100100011111		
Z5[1:0]	100100010010				100100010010		
Z6[1:0]	101011001110				101011001110		
Z7[1:0]	010010000001				010010000001		
Z8[1:0]	010011011011				010011011011		
Z9[1:0]	101111010010				101111010010		
Z10[1:0]	100000111111				100000111111		
Z11[1:0]	011110110001				011110110001		
Z12[1:0]	010110011101				010110011101		
Z13[1:0]	110111111001				110111111001		
Z14[1:0]	110000000100				110000000100		
Z15[1:0]	011000010110				011000010110		
Z16[1:0]	000101110111				000101110111		

Name	Value	000,004 sp	000,005 sp	000,006 sp	000,007 sp	000,008 sp	000,009 sp
217[1]14	10000100000			0000100000			
218[1]14	00010110011			00010110011			
219[1]14	00011110111			00011110111			
220[1]14	10101111000			10101111000			
221[1]14	10011000100			10011000100			
222[1]14	10100101000			10100101000			
223[1]14	01000111011			01000111011			
224[1]14	10000101011			10000101011			
225[1]14	10010011100			10010011100			
226[1]14	01100101010			01100101010			
227[1]14	01110100001			01110100001			
228[1]14	01111101100			01111101100			
229[1]14	01000111000			01000111000			
230[1]14	01100111001			01100111001			
231[1]14	10001010110			10001010110			
Clk	0						
rst	0						

RTL SCHEMATIC:

DESIGN SUMMARY:

Device Utilization Summary (estimated values)			
Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Number of Slices	1569	960	163%
Number of Slice Flip-Flops	640	1000	64%
Number of 4-input LUTs	2832	3600	78%
Number of bonded IOBs	674	88	766%
Number of BCLKs	1	24	4%

TIMING SUMMARY:

```

Timing constraint: Default OFFSET OUT AFTER for Clock 'CLK'
Total number of paths / destination ports: 384 / 384
-----
Offset: 4.040ns (Levels of Logic = 1)
Source: m2/Mby2SST2/YOUT_11 (FF)
Destination: E10<11> (WAD)
Source Clock: CLK rising

Data Path: m2/Mby2SST2/YOUT_11 to E10<11>
-----
Cell:in->out      fanout  Delay  Gate  Delay  Logical Name (Net Name)
-----
FDR:C->Q          1        0.514  0.357  m2/Mby2SST2/YOUT_11 (m2/Mby2SST2/YOUT_11)
CMUF:I->O        1        3.163          E10_11_CMUF (E10<11>)
-----
Total: 4.040ns (3.603ns logic, 0.357ns route)
(91.2% logic, 8.8% route)
    
```

VII. CONCLUSION

A quick integer operator To adapt to the HEVC standard for continuous ultra HD video coding, VLSI engineering-based insufficient SBT is suggested. With the effect of bit width on circuit delay in mind, the suggested VLSI engineering upgrades the bit width of the number change framework. The suggested lattice bit-plane degradation technique converts the full number change lattice with high-piece width components into many SBT lattices with low-piece width components. For low-piece-width computations, change engineering using SBT may be more productive. For the SBT in particular, the circuit reuse scheme is recommended in order to reduce the amount of adders in the VLSI design. When compared to prior studies, the suggested transform hardware design can process video data more quickly and in a more efficient area. The suggested circuit reuse technique significantly reduces the number of adders needed for the SBT.

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